

Sustainable Wastewater Management Practices for Dairy and Brewery Industries: Treatment, Reuse, and Beyond

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Abstract

The food and drink industry are the EU's leading manufacturing sector resulting in significant water and energy consumption. Despite advancements in water-use efficiency, efforts to minimize freshwater use during raw material processing remain limited. High water consumption drives up production costs, further exacerbated by rising wastewater treatment tariffs and industrial electricity prices in European cities. This study investigates the application of a pilot ultrafiltration (UF) and Ultraviolet (UV) disinfection system in a dairy and a brewery industry for industrial wastewater treatment and reuse. The treated effluent was assessed for onsite uses and irrigation suitability, with a focus on energy consumption and operational performance. Comparative analysis examined transmembrane pressure (TMP) increases, chemical cleaning frequency, and energy needs across both industries. Results indicate that UF/UV systems can significantly reduce water demand while ensuring adequate reclaimed water quality for reuse. Integrating these technologies offers a pathway to lower operational costs and mitigate environmental impact. This research underscores the importance of adopting a water-waste-energy nexus to enhance resource efficiency and promote circular water management in resource-intensive sectors. By providing practical insights into the scalability and feasibility of these systems, this work supports the food and beverage industry in addressing its environmental and economic challenges effectively.

Keywords

brewery industry; circular economy; dairy industry; micropollutants; reclaimed water; UF/UV

INTRODUCTION

Industrialization plays a vital role in the economic growth of countries, but it also poses significant environmental challenges, particularly in the food and beverage sector, due to excessive water consumption and high production of effluents per unit of production (Ahmad et al. 2019). Among these, the brewing and dairy industries are notable contributors to pollution due to their large-scale operations and waste generation. The food and beverage industry are the EU's largest manufacturing sector, consuming 56% of industrial and urban water and embedding 28% of production-related energy. Additionally, the industry generates 30.6 Mt of food waste annually, highlighting the need for sustainable practices.

The brewing industry, for instance, is an important economic segment globally, as beer is the fifth most consumed beverage worldwide, after tea, carbonates, milk, and coffee (L. Fillaudeau et al. 2007; Luc Fillaudeau, Blanpain-Avet, and Daufin 2006). Beer production involves brewing and packaging, generating by-products like spent grains and yeast surplus, which contribute to pollution when mixed with effluents (Doubla et al. 2007). Additionally, cleaning processes for tanks, bottles, machines, and floors generate substantial quantities of polluted water. It is estimated that producing 1 L of beer generates 3–10 L of wastewater, depending on specific production practices (Braeken, Van Der Bruggen, and Vandecasteele 2004; Luc Fillaudeau, Blanpain-Avet, and Daufin 2006; Kanagachandran and Jayaratne 2006).

Similarly, the dairy industry, which produces milk, milk powder, butter, and cheese, has experienced significant growth worldwide due to rising demand for dairy products (Chokshi et al. 2016). However, this growth also leads to increased pollution through the release of high-organic-content solid and liquid wastes, which pose a serious threat to the environment and human health (Porwal, Mane, & Velhal, 2015). Annually, the global dairy industry generates approximately 4–11 million tonnes of waste, threatening biodiversity (Porwal, Mane, and Velhal 2015; Chokshi et al. 2016).

This study presents the results of the application of two pilot ultrafiltration (UF) and Ultraviolet (UV) disinfection systems in a dairy and a brewery industry, to produce treated effluent suitable for unrestricted irrigation or industrial water reclamation. Both industries exemplify the environmental

costs of industrial growth, particularly through their voluminous water usage and the high organic content of their effluents, which, if untreated, cause severe damage to ecosystems and human health. Effective waste management strategies are critical to mitigating these impacts and ensuring sustainable industrial practices also in relation to the new EU directive (2024/3019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two identical pilot-scale ultrafiltration (UF) and ultraviolet (UV) disinfection systems were installed in a beverage and a dairy industry, respectively, in the industrial area of Patras. Each system treats secondary effluent from the respective wastewater treatment plant (WWTPs) of the two industries to meet both the EU and the Greek Water Reuse Standards (Figures 1 & 2). The UF system is equipped with membranes made of durable polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) material, featuring a nominal pore size of 0.04 μm . The membrane filtration process operates from outside to inside, achieving an average net flux of 31 L/m²/h. To maintain optimal performance, the system incorporates a three-stage cleaning process: (1) air flushing, (2) chemical maintenance cleaning (MC) using water, chlorine, and acid, and (3) chemical recovery cleaning (RC) with chlorine and acid.

Effluent from the WWTP is stored in a 10 m³ holding tank before being pumped into the UF system. The system has a treatment capacity of 5 m³/h and achieves a recovery rate exceeding 95%. To ensure consistent operation and high-quality output, the system is equipped with online sensors that continuously monitor critical parameters such as turbidity, conductivity, pH and temperature. The system operates fully automatically, with all processes managed by a programmable logic controller (PLC), ensuring precise control and reliability during operation.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the Main Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) and Tertiary UF/UV Treatment in the Brewery Industry

Figure 2: Flowchart of the Main Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) and Tertiary UF/UV in the Dairy Industry

Effluent water quality was evaluated based on Greek and EU legislation for unrestricted agricultural irrigation/ reuse. The analysis included conventional parameters (e.g., COD, BOD₅, TSS, NH₄⁺-N, NO₃⁻-N, EC, TC) and micropollutants, as required by EU Directive 2024/3019 on urban wastewater treatment examining the effectiveness of various treatment processes from food and beverage industries in reducing potential impacts on environmental receptors and human health. Sampling and testing were conducted both in the permeate water and in the field before and after irrigation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The UF-UV treatment system demonstrated excellent performance, producing effluent compliant with strict regulations for unrestricted agricultural irrigation. In the dairy industry, the treated effluent was further utilized as influent for the existing RO system, which supplies high-quality water to cooling towers at the dairy industry. For the brewery industry, the UF-UV effluent was evaluated for its suitability for unrestricted irrigation and met the required reclaimed water quality standards. The RO system for the dairy industry improved operational efficiency, reducing the membrane cleaning frequency to once per year. Future work will explore the possibility of directly feeding the UF-treated permeate to the RO system in the dairy industry, aiming to lower cooling tower cycles and achieve energy savings.

The treated effluent quality metrics showed average COD concentrations of 42 ± 12 mg/L (dairy) and 120 ± 82 mg/L (brewery), with BOD₅ values of 6 ± 5 mg/L and 8 ± 7 mg/L, respectively. TSS were fully removed in both cases, with no detectable levels. Turbidity was consistently low, below 1 NTU for dairy and 2 NTU for brewery effluents. Nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations were minimal, and EC and TC were undetectable.

The UF systems operated at stable transmembrane pressures (TMP) of 0.5 bar (dairy) and 0.3 bar (brewery), handling average flows of 5 m³/h and 2.5 m³/h, respectively. Figure 1 illustrates the distinct TMP profiles for the two industries.

Figure 3: Transmembrane pressure (TMP) profiles during operating cycles for the dairy and brewery UF systems.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the TMP for the brewery industry remains consistently low, while in the dairy industry, it shows a marked increase, though it remains below 1 bar throughout the operation. Figure 4 presents the profiles of micropollutants for the two industries, categorized into different groups. In compliance with the new EU regulations, the effectiveness of the UF treatment processes

in mitigating potential impacts on environmental receptors and human health was also assessed. The results indicated that there was no significant risk associated with the permeate water.

Figure 4: Micropollutant analysis profiles for the brewery (left) and for the dairy (right) industry

CONCLUSIONS

These findings demonstrate the effective performance of the UF-UV system in producing high-quality treated effluent that consistently meets the strict requirements of EU limits for unrestricted agricultural irrigation. Its implementation in Patras, treating 40 m³ of industrial wastewater daily in the food and beverage sector, showcases its reliability in managing pollutant loads. By integrating seamlessly with advanced RO processes, the system enhances operational efficiency while reducing energy demands and protecting membrane longevity. This technology offers a practical and sustainable solution for industrial water reuse, reflecting the balance between innovation and environmental responsibility.

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